

BUSINESS ETHICS AND CULTURE, RULES FOR ITS WORK

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KEYWORDS

universal moral standards,
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ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurial activity, entrepreneurial leader's ethics, entrepreneur's culture, mental-psychological features of entrepreneurial leader's activity, conflict situations in entrepreneurial leader's activity and ways to solve them. Code of ethics of businessmen evaluates methods and policies in the field of business, concepts of truth and fairness.

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TADBIRKORLIK ETIKASI VA MADANIYATI, UNI ISHLAB CHIQUISH QOIDALARI

KALIT SO‘ZLAR:

umumaxloqiy me'yorlar, tadbirkor va yollangan ishchilar, axloq kodeksi, tadbirkor madaniyati, hikmat adabi, xizmat adabi

ANNOTATSIYA

Tadbirkor faoliyati, tadbirkor rahbar etikasi, tadbirkor madaniyati, tadbirkor rahbar faoliyatining ruhiy- psixologik xususiyatlari, tadbirkor rahbar faoliyatida mojaroli holatlar va ularni hal etish usullari. Biznesmenlarning axloq kodeksi biznes sohasidagi. usul va siyosatni baholash, haqiqat va adolatlilik tushunchalari.

Tadbirkor faoliyati faqat tadbirkorlikning huquqiy va tashkiliy asoslariga bog'liq bo'lmasdan, u insonlar, o'zining qo'l ostida xizmat qiluvchi mutaxassislar va ishchilar, ayniqsa, chet ellik hamkasblari – biznesmenlar doirasida umumaxloqiy me'yorlarga rioya qilishi bilan ham bahoanadi. Ishdagi muvaffaqiyatning yarmidan ko'proqi uning odobiga, madaniyatiga, dunyoharashiga, ishbilarmonlik qoidalarini qay darajada bilishiga bevosita bog'liqdir.

tadbirkorlar ittifoqiga a'zolik, har bir tadbirkordan mazkur axloq kodeksiga rioya etilishini talab qiladi;

axloq kodeksiga amal qilmaslik va uning har qanday tamoyillarini buzish, ittifoqdagi muayyan a'zoning a'ziligini to'xtatish uchun asos bo'ladi. har bir alohida qol ittifoq boshqaruvi tomonidan ittifoq a'zosi ishtirokida ko'rib chiqiladi;

qaror ustidan shikoyat qilishga faqat tadbirkorlar ittifoqi s'ezdi oldidan imkoniyat mavjud bo'lib, uni bekor qilish yoki kuchda qoldirish masalasi ko'rilishi mumkin.

Ko'rib turibmizki, kodeksda gap tadbirkorning xulq-atvori me'yorlari to'g'risida, uning ish usuliga, kishilar bilan muomala qilish tabiatiga, ijtimoiy qiyofasiga nisbatan madaniy jamiyat qurayotgan talablar to'g'risida bormoqda.

Tadbirkor madaniyati

Tadbirkor madaniyati deganda tadbirkor adabi va iqtidori o'rtasidagi dialektik bog'lanish tushuniladi. Bu bog'lanish quyidagi fazilatlar majmuasida o'z aksini topadi:

Odob – aqlning suyanchiqi, barcha fazilatlarining mezoni. Bequdaga xalqimizda: “Aql bilan odob - egizak”, deyishmaydi. Odob – yaxshilik bilan yomonlikning farqini bilish, foyda bilan zarar orasidagi tafovutni anglashdir. Odob vositasida kishi o'z jonini yomon xislatlardan davolaydi, yoqimsiz ayblardan poklaydi, chiroyli fazilatlaridan bezaydi. Odob tadbirkorni eng chiroyli xulq bilan qurollantiradi. Natijada aql egalari bunday tadbirkordan har ishda rozi bo'lishadi. Odobli tadbirkor esa kundan kunga obro' topadi, nufuzi oshadi, ishlari ravnaq topadi. Ba'zi hakimlar odobni eng mas'um va ko'rkam fe'lga ega bo'lish desalar, ba'zilar nafsni barcha qabiq odatlardan tozalash deb ta'rif berishadi. Demak, tadbirkordagi odobning mavjudligi, bu noyob ne'matning mavjudligidir.

Umuman odob ikki xil bo'ladi:

hikmat odobi;
xizmat odobi.

hikmat odobi poklik va to'g'ri yo'lga etaklaydi. Xizmat odobi esa badavlatlik va obro'ga etkazadi. har ikkisi ham uluq fazilat bo'lib, biri aziz qilsa, ikkinchisi qudratli qiladi. Odob rahbarni aql va axloq egasi bo'lishga, vijdonli, or-nomusli, sof ko'ngilli, subutli bo'lishga da'vat etadi. Iymon arabcha so'z bo'lib, lug'aviy ma'nosi – ishonchdir.

Sodda qilib aytganda:

Iymon uya narsaning butunligidan hosil bo'ladi: e'tiqod, iqror va amal. E'tiqod – bu ishonch. Iqror – so'zda buni tan olish. Amal – yaxshi ishlar bilan uni isbotlash.

Insof – bu adolat va vijdon amri bilan ish tutish tuyg'usi va qobiliyati, ishda, kishilarga munosabatda halollik, to'g'rilik. Barobarlik, sofdillik va haqiqatgo'ylikdir. O'zgani o'z o'rniga va shuningdek, o'zini o'zgani o'rniga xayolan qo'yib ko'rish ham insofga kiradi. Yuqorida ta'kidlaganimizdek, to'q ochni, boy kambag'alni, baxtli baxtsizni, tolei baland tolei zabunni, omadli omadsizni, sog'lom va bemorni o'z o'rniga qo'yib ko'rolsa va aksincha ham xuddi shunday bo'lsa olam guliston – insofililar safi ko'payaveradi.

Adolat – bu barcha fazilatlar ichidagi eng oliy fazilatdir. Adolatparvar tadbirkor yoki rahbarning axloqiy qislatlari bemalol qonun o'rnini bosa oladi. Ulug' alloma Nasriddin Tusiy ijtimoiy adolatning uch asosiy talabi mavjudligini va jamiyat taraqqiyotini belgilovchi muhim omil ekanini alohida uqtirgan edi:

Xulosa Maqsadlarni amalga oshirish uchun mamlakatimiz miqyosida quyidagi masalalarni hal qilish lozim:

- bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida ishlash uchun kadrlar tayyorlash va ularning malakasini oshirish;
- hududlarda haqiqiy tadbirkorlik muhitiini yaratish;
- kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni moliyaviy jihatdan qo'llab-quvvatlash;
- kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikning huquqiy bazasini mustahkamlash;
- kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni texnologik jihozlar bilan ta'minlashni qo'llab-quvvatlash;
- islohotlar natijalarini reklama va axborot xizmati vositalari orqali keng ommaga etkazish.

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